

A Study on Importance of Butterflies and Moths in Taranagar Region of Churu District of Rajasthan (India)

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Abstract

Butterflies and moths are belonging from the order Lepidoptera of class Insecta. Butterflies raise the gladness of gardens, flowery meadow color and image of sunshine. After honey bee, butterflies are the greater contributor for pollinating flowering plants and economically important crops. On earth moths are also diverse insect group. They are ranging from smallest to largest in size and shape. Silk or fiber industries are totally dependent on lepidopterans, so if the lepidopterans population is decrease or decline than the agricultural and fiber industries are directly affected. There are many causes for importance of butterflies and moths in their own rights. Butterflies are work as ecosystems service suppliers and also effort as indicator of environmental health. Moths shapes the composition and structure of habitats because they play important role in food chain as a key links. In this article author presented a complete information about the importance of butterflies and moths in Taranagar region of Churu district.

Keywords

Butterflies, Moths, Crops, Pollination, Taranagar, Churu.

Introduction

In insects butterflies and moths are very diverse group that are belonging from Lepidoptera order of class Insecta of Arthropoda phylum. Animals found in Arthropoda phylum has jointed appendages so insects have also jointed appendages. Their body is divided into three basal parts such as – Head, Thorax and Abdomen. They have three pairs of jointed leg so these are known as Hexapods. The term 'Lepidoptera' means- 'Scaly wing'. Two pairs of scaly wings are found on the meso- and meta- thorax region of both the butterflies and moths. So that these are also known as lepidopterans and the study of lepidopterans are known as "lepidopterology".

Butterflies and moths are graceful for ecosystem and few species may cause and any damage to some commercial plants. Lepidopterans contributed to indicate the health of environment and an ecosystem service. After bees they play an important role to pollinate flowering plants and major economically important crops. Silk industries are totally dependent on lepidopterans.

Butterflies and moths are going through complete metamorphosis because their life is completed in four stages - Eggs, Larvae, Pupa and Adult. Firstly, they lay their eggs on host plants. From eggs larvae is emerges that is called as caterpillars. From the beginning of emergence, caterpillars are start to feed and they are continuously feeding on host plant. Feeding is stop with the transformation of caterpillar into pupa. Now development occurs inside the pupa and an adult butterfly or moth is came out from it. Duration of life of lepidopterans are very short. It is from one day to two weeks only. Finding of favorable host plant and matting partner and egg laying occur during this period. Apart from pollen grains and nectar of flowers they also feed on decaying matter or any other part of plants and dead animals, etc. Butterflies are delicate for climatic switching.

Aim of study

1. To investigate the importance of butterflies and moths in different industries and crop field.
2. To know about importance of moths in food chain of ecosystem.
3. To enhance the knowledge and public awareness about lepidopterans.

Review of Literature

Various types of literature available on the importance of butterflies and moths such as various articles, research articles, research papers and books etc. have been prominently covered in this

literature review. The summary of the major research work done by various researchers is as follows- -

Work on effectiveness and importance of butterflies as pollinators to the flowers of *Ixora Coccinea* was done by Duara (2014). The author concluded that pollination by butterfly increases the number of fruits per plant and the number of fruits per bunch.

A study on overview of biological control of economically important lepidopteran pests with parasitoids was done by Salim *et al.*, (2016). The present review suggested that the insect order Lepidoptera is one of the most important order with many pests' species of agriculture produce.

Studies on butterflies and their contribution in ecosystem: a review was done by Ghazanfar *et al.*, (2016). In this study, the authors worked on the important role of butterflies in ecosystem. Butterflies are wild indicators of the ecosystem. In this study authors find out that the contribution of butterflies to a healthy ecosystem and pollination is incomparable.

A detailed account of the lepidopterans of economic importance in Cameroon; A systematic review was provided by Ouaba *et al.*, (2022). In this study authors provides special information on economic importance of lepidopterans. This study shows that lepidopterans are valuable in silk production, industry, decoration etc.

A study on common moths and their ecological importance in Bisra Range, Rourkela forest division, Odisha, India was done by Pradhan *et al.*, (2024). In this research, authors reported about 20 species of common moths from the study area. This study concluded that Moths are important pollinators as well as important links in the food chain in ecosystems hence this study highlight the ecological importance of moths.

Study area: In India, Rajasthan is the largest state by geographical area. It covers approx. 10.4% landmass of India. In the geographical map of India, Rajasthan situated at 28⁰ 41'N 75⁰³'E. Taranagar region of Rajasthan is located at Churu district that is the north area of the state. It is a deserted area of the state. Temperature is found on extreme level in both summer and winter. In summer the temperature goes above 50 °C whereas in winter it is noticed below 0°C or in minus. Food scarcity, lack of water and dry winds are some of the key features of this area. Dry winds go along in summer are known as "Loo".

Methodology

The study was undertaken monthly for a period of 7 months from August 2023 to February 2024.

Method: For this study Survey method, Direct observation method and many other methods were used by author. Survey is done in different villages around Taranagar tehsil. Questionary with farmers of agricultural field also used to know about the pollination of crops.

Material: Camera, binocular, mobile phone, hand lens etc. things are used for observing butterflies and moths in study area.

Result and Discussion

1. Sensitization for Climate Switching – Butterflies are very delicate for climate switching. Researcher studied on butterflies as a method to watching the signal of warning to the more dispersed effect of climatic changes.

2. Education and Research –The life cycle of moths and butterflies is fantastic about educational purpose. It teaches about natural world of earth. These are also important for research purpose. The diversity of lepidopterans found in different seasons, different families of lepidopterans found in study area, scaled or scale less wings, the pattern of wings such as shape, size etc. are some other aspects for study or research value. Butterflies are uses as model organisms to study climate changes, habitat loss, in field of navigation, embryology, pest control, mimicry, evolution, genetics, biodiversity conservation, etc.

3. Indicator of Healthy Ecosystem–Moths and Butterflies indicate about the health of an ecosystem or healthy environment. They indicate the number of other invertebrates is high in the area because both the groups of lepidopterans serve a broad range of environmental benefits such as natural pest controller, etc. Nocturnal moths that are attracted toward light are mostly seen to act as food for lizard in houses.

4. Key Link of Natural Food Chain – Moths and butterflies play important role in natural food chain. They act as prey for other organisms such as – bats, birds, lizards and other insectivorous animals. In the food chain these are serves themselves as primary consumers.

5. Increase Biodiversity – Butterflies and moth evolve as much as other species. They play a major role to rich biodiversity of any ecosystem. For some general and specific invertebrate butterflies act as flagship species. Animals depends on lepidopterans are increase in number as the number of lepidopterans are increases.

6. Economic value – Moth and butterfly affect negatively in economic value. They act as pest on agricultural major pest including Noctuidae, Pyralidae, etc. so the number of crop pest are reduced and crop become more harvested.

7. Pollination – Lepidopterans are very well pollinators after bees. Butterflies are active during day and visit one flower to the other. During their visit the pollen grains of the flower are sticks to their body and disperse on another flower. Their six jointed legs, one pair of antennae, head, thorax and cylindrical abdomen, etc. makes them a very good pollinator.

8. Entertainment –Butterflies and moths are very pretty insects. It increases the beauty of gardens and parks. Sometimes people paly with butterfly to catch it, so it is also important for fun and happiness.

Conclusion

Insects are very widely distributed group of animals. Butterflies and moths are very special group of insects. These are combinedly known as Lepidopterans. This research provides the special information about importance of moths and butterflies found in Taranagar region of Churu district. These have sense for climate switching and act as indicator of a healthy ecosystem.

Some butterfly and most of the nocturnal moths are play major role in important link of food chain. These are act as primary consumers in natural food chain. These are highly use as scientific education and research purpose. They increase biodiversity of other invertebrate to serve own as prey of them. Butterflies and moths are very good pollinators after bees. These are uses for fun and entertainment. Thus this study provides a clear picture of importance of butterflies and moths in study area.

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